

**Molecular Interactions in Mixed Monolayers at the
Water/Air Interface***
(Interactions between Longchain Normal Fatty Alcohols)

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Pressure-area isotherms on water surface, of mixed monolayers of hexadecanol (C_{16} -OH), as well as octadecanol (C_{18} -OH) with docosanol (C_{22} -OH) were studied as a function of mole fraction and temperature. Both positive and negative deviations from additivity rule, $A_{12} = A_1N_1 + A_2N_2$, were observed for both the mixtures. Positive deviations were observed at lower temperatures and pressures. These deviations were attributed to the changes taking place as a result of packing of the molecules in the monolayer state. It has been postulated that the existence of several different types of surface lattices in which substitutional type of solid solution has occurred without any modification of the reticular structure.

Studies on the structural and related physical properties of insoluble mixed monolayers at the water/air interface are of considerable technical and biological importance. The possibility of practical utilization of mixed monolayers such as that of cetyl and stearyl alcohols to minimise evaporation loss of water stored in lakes and reservoirs¹ is being seriously considered, because the performance of such films may improve over that of the pure components in several ways as giving rise to better spreading power, formation of more condensed structure and stability. Furthermore, these commercially prepared fatty alcohols warrant direct use as they are composed of difficultly resolvable mixtures whose separation involve excessive cost. Phospho-lipids and lipo-proteins are major constituents of biological membranes. An elucidation of the structure of mixed films formed by these constituents would provide an insight into the nature of their interactions with and transport properties of molecules present in natural biological systems.

Many of the earlier investigations on monolayer properties at the water/air interface employed measurements of surface pressure, potential and viscosity at different compositions in a Langmuir trough. In binary mixtures where each component is capable of

* Dedicated to Prof. Santi R. Palit on the occasion of his 60th birth anniversary.

independent monolayer existence, the film properties were generally found to exhibit either negative or positive deviations from the ideal mixture law,

$$A_{12} = A_1N_1 + A_2N_2$$

where A_1 , A_2 are areas per molecule in the pure films, A_{12} is the mean area per molecule in the mixed films and N_1 and N_2 are mole fractions.

Negative deviations have however, been found more frequently³. Adam and Jessop⁴ observed condensation in mixtures of cholesterol with myristic acid and oleic acid. Report of positive deviations appear to be less common. A few notable examples⁵ are mixtures of oleic, cis-9,5 dihydroxyl octadecanoic and erucic acids with cis-13,14 dihydroxy eicosonic acid. Recently, Quintana *et al.*^{6,7} observed both positive and negative deviations in mixed films of L- α -lecithin and grison derivatives, and hexachlorophene monostearate with stearyl alcohol, stearic acid, stearyl acelate and tristearin. Cadenhead and Phillips⁸ also reported similar deviations.

Several workers attempted to explain the nonideal behaviour involving complex formation through specific molecular interactions such as van der Waals, dipole-dipole, ion-dipole attractions or repulsions including involvement of steric factors and hydrogen bonding. Unfortunately, those films consisted of molecules with complex shapes, steric factors and functional groups making interpretation of the results in terms of specific molecular interactions and packing too difficult. As a matter of fact Shah⁹ and Schulman explained that the negative deviations could as well happen due to one type of molecules going into the intermolecular cavities formed in lattice structure of the other component. It is clearly desirable to extend similar studies to mixed monolayers formed by simpler molecules as models to elucidate their structure and the nature of the molecular interactions providing nonideal behaviour.

We have therefore undertaken an investigation of the properties of monolayers formed by normal fatty alcohols. The molecules consist of a straight hydrocarbon chain with a small polar-OH at one end. In this communication are reported the results of the pressure-area (π -A) isotherm studies of insoluble monolayers formed by mixtures of cetyl (C_{16} -OH) and stearyl (C_{18} -OH) alcohols with behenyl (C_{22} -OH) alcohol, at the water-air interface.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials : All the laboratory grade long chain alcohols (C_{16} -OH, C_{18} -OH and C_{22} -OH) of the B.D.H. or Fluka make, were first purified by fractional crystallization. These were then acetylated, fractionally distilled, deacetylated and fractionally crystallized. The final products showed constant melting points and were finally tested in a gas chromatograph, which showed better than 99.9% purity.

Analar grade petroleum ether (*n*-hexane) was fractionally distilled and the middle fraction boiling in the range 62°-65° was used as the spreading solvent.

[*Procedure* : The experimental procedure followed for obtaining π -A data were essentially the same as described earlier^{10,11}, with some modifications. The edges of the Langmuir trough were made more sharp which helped to compress the film to higher pressures (upto

TABLE I
Pressure-area values at phase transformation point

C ₁₆ -OH + C ₂₂ -OH														
Mole fraction of C ₂₂ -OH Phase transition	0.0			0.25			0.50			0.75			1.0	
Temp.	15°	20°	25°	15°	20°	25°	15°	20°	25°	15°	20°	25°	20°	25°
$\pi_G \rightarrow L_c$ (A)	0.2 (19.94)	0.4 (19.98)	0.6 (20.64)	0.2 (20.84)	0.3 (20.48)	0.4 (20.92)	0.3 (20.28)	0.4 (20.53)	0.6 (21.16)	0.3 (20.34)	0.4 (20.60)	0.5 (21.20)	0.3 (21.44)	0.4 (21.10)
$\pi_{Lc} \rightarrow LS$ or S (A)	9.8 (18.88)	10.3 (19.00)	10.7 (19.48)	6.2 (19.85)	5.4 (19.64)	5.3 (20.20)	8.4 (19.17)	9.2 (19.34)	4.6 (20.07)	9.1 (18.91)	12.2 (19.28)	5.1 (20.45)	11.2 (18.43)	23.2 (18.75)
$\pi_{LS} \rightarrow S$ (A)	—	—	—	24.0 (19.31)	22.4 (19.20)	—	23.2 (18.58)	23.2 (18.92)	—	23.2 (18.48)	23.0 (19.00)	—	—	—
A_{010}	19.06	19.12	19.68	19.66	19.48	20.31	18.87	19.22	20.05	18.80	19.24	20.06	18.44	19.74

C ₁₈ -OH + C ₂₂ -OH														
Mole fraction of C ₂₂ -OH Phase transition	0.0			0.25			0.50			0.75			1.0	
Temp.	15°	20°	25°	15°	20°	25°	15°	20°	25°	15°	20°	25°	20°	25°
$\pi_G \rightarrow L_c$ (A)	0.2 (19.86)	0.3 (20.20)	0.4 (20.74)	0.2 (20.46)	0.4 (20.50)	0.6 (20.54)	0.4 (20.34)	0.4 (20.00)	0.5 (20.28)	0.2 (20.60)	0.3 (20.20)	0.4 (20.18)	0.2 (20.34)	0.3 (21.44)
$\pi_{Lc} \rightarrow LS$ or S (A)	13.0 (18.51)	13.2 (18.74)	13.8 (19.22)	6.7 (19.26)	8.2 (19.33)	9.4 (19.40)	8.0 (19.14)	6.8 (18.94)	7.7 (19.24)	9.2 (19.36)	12.2 (18.94)	9.4 (18.91)	11.2 (18.43)	23.2 (18.75)
$\pi_{LS} \rightarrow S$ (A)	—	—	—	22.2 (18.92)	24.2 (18.96)	24.4 (19.18)	23.2 (18.80)	24.8 (18.47)	23.2 (18.94)	24.2 (18.98)	24.2 (18.68)	24.2 (18.60)	—	—
A_{010}	18.66	18.90	19.44	19.24	19.27	19.38	19.04	18.76	19.20	19.25	18.90	18.82	18.44	19.74

about 45 dynes/cm) without spilling of water over the trough. Teflon barriers were used for compressing the films. Measured quantities of 0.005*M* solutions of the *n*-alcohols in *n*-hexane were delivered with the help of a Agla micrometer syringe to the clean surface of double distilled water in a thermostated Langmuir trough. The water surface temperature was measured to an accuracy of $\pm 0.05^\circ$ with a L-shaped thermistor probe specially made for this purpose. Fresh solutions were employed for each and every experiment. Two or three pilot runs were initially conducted to determine the general trend of the π -*A* isotherms and the regions of phase transition approximately which were later investigated carefully. Final runs were made after repeated casting of a number of films from fresh solutions. The reproducibility of area and pressure measurements under similar experimental conditions was within $\pm 0.1 \text{ \AA}^2$ and 0.1 dyne/cm respectively. Scrupulous cleaning of the trough and all other ancillaries coming into contact with the monolayer was performed after each experiment.

RESULTS

$\text{C}_{16}\text{-OH} + \text{C}_{22}\text{-OH}$ and $\text{C}_{18}\text{-OH} + \text{C}_{22}\text{-OH}$

The pressure-area (π -*A*) isotherms of the pure $\text{C}_{16}\text{-OH}$ and $\text{C}_{18}\text{-OH}$ and their mixtures containing 0.0, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75 and 1.0 mole fractions of $\text{C}_{22}\text{-OH}$ at three different temperatures (15.1° , 19.9° and 25.0°) are illustrated in Figs. 1-6.

In the isotherms of the components, the film molecules show a gas-like (*G*) state at low pressures. On further compression a liquid-condensed (*L_s*) and finally a solid (*S*) state regions appear. In the cases of mixed films, an additional intermediate liquid-solid (*LS*) state is noticeable. The observed π and *A* values at the $G \rightarrow L_c$, $L_c \rightarrow LS$ or *S* and $LS \rightarrow S$ transition points are noted in Table 1. The limiting area per molecule, expressed as $A_{0(s)}$, obtained as usual by extrapolation of the straight line of the solid state region to zero pressure ($\pi = 0$), are also recorded. Some of these π and *A* values may be considered as rather approximate due to diffuse nature of the curves at the transition points.

For facility of comparison, our values of $A_{0(s)}$ and $\pi_{L_c \rightarrow s}$ of the pure components are noted in Table 2 along with those reported in the literature. These values have been obtained from isotherms at slightly different temperatures which are noted in parenthesis in the table. In general it is found that the isotherms and the transition points appearing in the literature are in good agreement with our results.

The effect of temperature on the amount of expansion or condensation properties of the films of the three pure alcohols viz., $\text{C}_{16}\text{-OH}$, $\text{C}_{18}\text{-OH}$ and $\text{C}_{22}\text{-OH}$, as measured by the change in area per molecule (denoted by ΔA) with temperature, have been estimated at five arbitrarily chosen pressures for a rise of temperature by 5° . These results have been expressed as the thermal area expansion coefficient $\beta = \Delta A / \Delta T$ and recorded in Table 3.

A positive value of β indicates expansion of the film due to an increase of temperature and a negative value indicates contraction. It is noticed that for $\text{C}_{16}\text{-OH}$ and $\text{C}_{18}\text{-OH}$ the value of β is always positive as expected normally. The expansion is comparatively less in the range 15° - 20° than in the range 20° - 25° . However, it is interesting to see that $\text{C}_{22}\text{-OH}$

TABLE 2

(The values in the bracket represent temperature)

Compounds	15.1°		19.9°		25°		
	Area/mol $A_{0(s)}$	$\pi_{L_c \rightarrow S}$	Area/mol $A_{0(s)}$	$\pi_{L_c \rightarrow S}$	Area/mol $A_{0(s)}$	$\pi_{L_c \rightarrow S}$	
Deo's work ^a	C ₁₆ -OH	19.98(17.2°)	9.8	21.33(21.02°)	10.4	20.52(25.2°)	10.6
	C ₁₈ -OH	19.74(16.18°)	12.4	21.14(21.01°)	13.1	20.92(24.9°)	13.8
	C ₂₂ -OH	19.52(17.9°)	20.0	21.10(21.2°)	21.0	19.62(25.01°)	23.0
Kuchhal's work ^b	C ₁₆ -OH	19.02(14.2°)	9.8	19.06(19.2°)	10.1	19.70(24.4°)	10.8
	C ₁₈ -OH	18.70(14.4°)	12.8	18.92(19.6°)	13.4	19.45(24.6°)	13.6
	C ₂₂ -OH	18.45(14.4°)	13.3	19.65(18.6°)	20.0	19.15(24.6°)	22.5
Present work	C ₁₆ -OH	19.05(15.1°)	9.8	19.12(19.9°)	10.2	17.70(25°)	10.6
	C ₁₈ -OH	19.66(15.1°)	13.0	18.88(19.9°)	13.2	19.42(25°)	13.8
	C ₂₂ -OH	18.40(15.1°)	13.2	19.74(19.9°)	20.2	19.03(25°)	23.0

a) A. V. Deo, S. B. Kulkarni, M. K. Gharpurey and A. B. Biswas, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, **2**, 43.b) Y. K. Kuchhal, S. S. Katti and A. B. Biswas, *J. Coll. and Infor. Sc.*, 1969, **29**, 521.

TABLE 3

 $\beta = \Delta A / \Delta T \rightarrow$ Average area expansion coefficient

Pressure π dynes/cm	C ₁₆ -OH		C ₁₈ -OH		C ₂₂ -OH	
	15°-20°	20°-25°	15°-20°	20°-25°	15°-20°	20°-25°
2	+0.01	+0.13	+0.07	+0.11	+0.23	-0.06
4	+0.02	+0.12	+0.06	+0.11	+0.26	-0.06
14	+0.026	+0.10	+0.05	+0.10	+0.31	-0.04
26	+0.04	+0.08	+0.04	+0.09	+0.16	-0.06
34	+0.046	+0.07	+0.04	+0.08	+0.13	-0.03

film expands in the range 15°-20° but contracts in the range 20°-25°, at all the five pressures. Further comparing the β values in the range 15°-20° an increase is indicated with the increase of chain length of the molecule but it is significantly much larger for the C₂₂-OH. This suggests that the intermolecular attraction in the film state decreases in the order C₁₆-OH > C₁₈-OH > C₂₂-OH, whereas in the bulk state of these molecules it is in the reverse order if their melting points are taken as rough indicator of the same.

Referring to the isotherms of the mixtures of C₁₆-OH and C₂₂-OH at 15° (Fig. 1), it is interesting to note that the isotherm 2 representing 0.25 mole fraction of C₂₂-OH looks considerably expanded compared to those of the pure components. As the amount of C₂₂-OH is increased, the isotherms (3 and 4) indicate closer packing of the film molecules occupying positions intermediate between the pure components (1 and 5). At 19.9° (Fig. 2) the mixed films occupy positions in between those of the components except in the highly compressed region (*S*-state). At 25° (Fig. 3) all the mixed monolayer isotherms lie in the intermediate position in the *L_c* and *LS* regions but indicate more expanded film state in the *S*-region.

Fig. 1. Pressure-area isotherms of hexadecanol, docosanol and their mixtures at different mole fractions at 15.1° .

On examining the isotherms of the mixture of $C_{18}\text{-OH}$ and $C_{22}\text{-OH}$, one may note the following characteristic features. At 15° (Fig. 4) all the mixed films are significantly more expanded than the pure components throughout all the pressure range studied. This behaviour is in contrast with what we observed earlier in the case of $C_{16}\text{-OH}$ containing films under similar conditions. Of the three mixtures, the equimolecular one is more condensed than those containing 0.25 and 0.75 mole fractions of $C_{22}\text{-OH}$, the latter forming the most expanded film. At 19.9° (Fig. 5), the isotherms of the mixed films occupy positions in between those of the pure components, the equimolar mixture (isotherm 3) again forming the most condensed system throughout all the pressure ranges. At 25° (Fig. 6), in the L_c or LS region, the mixed films are more condensed than the pure components, and in the S -region these occupy more or less intermediate positions, with the exception of the film

containing 0.75 mole fraction of C_{22} -OH (isotherm 4) which appears most condensed throughout the pressure range studied.

Fig. 2. Pressure-area isotherm of hexadecanol, docosanol and their mixtures at different mole fractions at 19.9° .

To investigate the molecular interaction and the packing or steric factors involved in the mixed film state, we can compare the observed A_{12} and π_{12} data with those calculated according to the mixture law relation, as indicated earlier, the amount of deviations determining the ideal or the extent of non-ideal behaviour. Accordingly we calculated the deviations from the equations

$$\delta A = (A_{12})_{obs} - (N_1 A_1 + N_2 A_2) \text{ at constant } \pi$$

$$\delta \pi = (\pi_{12})_{obs} - (N_1 \pi_1 + N_2 \pi_2) \text{ at constant area/molecule}$$

Fig. 3. Pressure-area isotherms of hexadecanol, docosanol and their mixtures at different mole fractions at 25°.

where δA is the difference between the observed area/molecule (A_{12}) in the mixed film state, and that calculated according to mixture law; N_1 and N_2 are the mole fractions of the two component alcohols; A_1 and A_2 are the corresponding area/molecule, all at some arbitrarily fixed pressures π of 2, 4, 14, 26 and 34 dynes/cm. Similarly $\delta\pi$ is the difference between the observed pressure (π_{12}) in the mixed state and that calculated according to the mixture law, all at some arbitrarily fixed area/molecule, of 19.2, 19.4, 19.8 and 20.2 Å²/molecule. These results are presented in tables 4 and 5.

Fig. 4. Pressure-area isotherms of octadecanol, docosanol and their mixtures at different mole fractions at 15.1°.

The positive value of δA indicates the expanded and negative value of condensed nature of the film. Some of these results are illustrated graphically in Fig. 7 for 5 different pressures and three temperatures. It may be noticed in general that for the C_{16} -OH alcohol system, high surface pressures and temperatures have a tendency to produce positive deviations. Further an increase in the proportion of the higher chain length compounds (C_{22} -OH) has a marked influence to produce negative deviations. This effect again seems to become smaller when the surface pressure is gradually increased as can be seen for the same mixed system at a fixed temperature. The marked influence of temperature in producing negative deviations is clearly seen in the case of the mixed systems containing C_{18} -OH. At 15° the

TABLE 4

$$\Delta A = [A_{12}]_{obs} - [N_1 A_1 + N_2 A_2]$$

Second component in the film	Pressure π dy/cm	Mole fraction of C ₂₂ -OH			Mole fraction of C ₂₂ -OH		
		0.25	0.50	0.75	0.25	0.50	0.75
15.1° C ₁₈ -OH	2	+0.73	+0.14	-0.12	+0.33	+0.09	+0.31
	4	+0.82	+0.13	-0.08	+0.31	+0.12	+0.35
	14	+0.94	+0.34	+0.26	+0.66	+0.61	+0.88
	26	+0.78	+0.02	+0.15	+0.51	+0.48	+0.71
	34	+0.82	+0.04	+0.15	+0.50	+0.50	+0.72
19.9° C ₁₈ -OH	2	+0.02	-0.34	-0.47	-0.03	-0.89	-0.85
	4	-0.12	-0.40	-0.48	-0.08	-0.92	-0.90
	14	+0.26	-0.23	-0.44	+0.19	-0.54	-0.70
	26	+0.32	0.0	+0.01	+0.24	-0.34	-0.24
	34	+0.38	+0.07	+0.14	+0.28	-0.26	-0.09
25° C ₁₈ -OH	2	+0.09	-0.12	+0.15	-0.29	-0.68	-0.83
	4	+0.02	-0.30	+0.02	-0.31	-0.71	-0.75
	14	+0.52	+0.30	+0.19	-0.02	-0.32	-0.74
	26	+0.73	+0.63	+0.76	+0.10	+0.02	-0.21
	34	+0.67	+0.59	+0.74	+0.14	+0.06	-0.16

TABLE 5

$$\delta\pi = (\pi_{12})_{obs} - [N_1\pi_1 + N_2\pi_2]$$

Temp.	Films spread to Area/mole Å ²	C ₁₈ -OH + C ₂₂ -OH Mole fraction of C ₂₂ -OH			C ₁₈ -OH + C ₂₂ -OH Mole fraction of C ₂₂ -OH		
		0.25	0.50	0.75	0.25	0.50	0.75
15.1°	19.20	+25.0	+ 1.1	0.0	+ 3.0	+ 0.9	+ 8.7
	19.40	+15.5	+ 0.9	- 0.3	+ 1.5	+ 1.0	+ 3.2
	19.80	+ 6.2	+ 1.2	- 0.5	+ 2.7	+ 1.1	+ 2.8
	20.20	+ 3.9	+ 0.4	- 0.4	+ 0.9	+ 0.5	+ 1.5
19.9°	19.20	+11.3	- 0.9	- 2.9	+ 2.0	- 8.4	- 9.4
	19.40	+ 5.5	- 2.5	- 4.4	- 2.0	- 8.0	- 7.3
	19.80	- 0.9	- 3.4	- 9.2	- 0.9	- 7.8	- 7.8
	20.20	- 1.1	- 3.7	- 5.2	- 0.4	- 5.5	- 8.2
25°	19.20	—	—	—	+ 1.9	- 7.3	- 9.7
	19.40	+28.1	+18.1	+20.5	- 3.9	- 7.6	- 8.7
	19.80	+15.2	+ 6.1	+ 2.8	- 3.3	- 6.8	- 8.3
	20.20	- 0.3	- 2.8	- 1.8	- 2.6	- 6.1	- 7.6

systems show positive deviations whereas at 20° and 25° they show strong negative deviations from the mixture law. Also in the $C_{16}\text{-OH} + C_{22}\text{-OH}$ system, the strong positive deviations observed at 15° are appreciably increased at higher temperatures of 20° and 25°.

Fig. 5. Pressure-area isotherms of octadecanol, docosanol and their mixtures at different mole fractions at 19.9°.

It may be seen in table 5 that all the $\delta\pi$ values at 15° for both $C_{16}\text{-OH} + C_{22}\text{-OH}$ and $C_{18}\text{-OH} + C_{22}\text{-OH}$ systems are positive except for one composition in the first system containing 0.75 mole fraction of $C_{22}\text{-OH}$. At 20° and 25° with the exception of a few, these mixtures show a negative deviation which tend to become smaller and eventually show positive deviations as the area per molecule is decreased or surface pressure increased as noted above.

In Fig. 8 the free energy of mixing (ΔG^M) as a function of mole fraction of C_{22} -OH at different temperatures have been plotted. These ΔG^M values have been estimated assuming the equilibrium relations ($\pi = 35$ dynes/cm) discussed by Goodrich¹². In the present studies the total free energy change (ΔG^M) in the mixing process has been calculated by using the following equation

$$\Delta G^M = \int_{\pi=0}^{\pi} (A_{12} - N_1 A_1 - N_2 A_2) d\pi + RT(N_1 \ln N_1 + N_2 \ln N_2)$$

Fig. 6. Pressure-area isotherms of octadecanol, docosanol and their mixtures at different mole fractions at 25°.

The magnitude and sign of ΔG^M normally provide information about the stability of the mixed film. Since the free energy change in forming an ideal mixed film is given by the $N_i \ln N_i$ term alone, the excess free energy of mixing is given by

$$\Delta G^{xs} = \int_{\pi=0}^{\pi} (A_{12} - N_1 A_1 - N_2 A_2) d\pi$$

Fig. 7. Average area per molecule as a function of mole fraction of docosanol at different temperatures.

The maximum reduction in free energy appears to occur near mole fraction 0.5 in the temperature range studied, but even there the excess free energy of mixing does not exceed 0.25 Kcal/mole. This interaction energy apparently does not appreciably result from chain-chain interaction. However, at 19.9° the maximum reduction in free energy (~ 1.2 Kcal/mole) occurs near about 0.25 mole fraction and the excess free energy of mixing is of the order of 0.6 to 0.7 Kcal/mole indicating stronger chain-chain interactions.

Fig. 8. Free energy of mixing as a function of mole fraction of docosanol at different temperatures.

DISCUSSION

It is well known that the normal fatty alcohol molecules which consist of a long alkyl chain and a polar end group (-OH) interact with each other and with water molecules and form an insoluble monolayer on a water surface. At extremely high molecular areas (A) the monolayer can be considered (G -state) as a dilute surface solution of the polar end and the alkyl chain (hydrophobic part) projected in air above the surface of water and oriented randomly with respect to the vertical.

Fig. 9.

The molecules may under this condition behave in an ideal way. As the area is decreased, intermolecular interactions start and the monolayer shows non-ideal behaviour and at a certain area transforms into a concentrated surface solution (L_c - or LS -state). The L_c -phase displays a liquid-like behaviour and the LS -phase represent a quasi-crystalline state

where the film molecules have some freedom of rotational motion and orient nearly vertical to the surface of water. The surface pressure of the concentrated surface solution changes very rapidly with further decrease in area and finally, a transition to a solid phase (*S*-state) occurs, with the film molecules oriented more or less vertically. The solid film itself may exist in a few different states (polymorphism—the formation of different types of surface lattices such as triangular, square or hexagonal) giving rise to different packing density, i.e., area/molecule, of the film molecules. The above mentioned transitions are actually observed in a π -*A* isotherm in the form of breaks or kinks.

The nature of the interactions can be understood by considering the fatty alcohol as unionised molecules which form condensed monolayer through intermolecular hydrogen bonding and chain-chain interaction (van der Waals attractive forces). Further, the end -OH group will have dipolar character (C_n-O-H^+) and at low area values gives rise to either attractive or repulsive interaction depending on the relative positions of the charged atoms in the neighbouring molecules in the monolayer. The molecular packing under different conditions of surface pressures are depicted in Fig. 9. Another factor to consider is the role of water molecules in the interface, which is also of importance in determining the overall structure.

The formation of an expanded or condensed type of film in the mixed state is no doubt a reflection of the rearrangement in packing and/or orientation of the molecules in the two-dimensional lattice. The expansion could also occur at low surface pressures if patches or islands formed by one component through intermolecular association, is dispersed due to the incorporation of the second component. The normal effect of temperature would be to shift the isotherm to larger areas due to thermal expansion of the film.

In the light of the above considerations we may analyse and correlate our results. Referring to Table 1 one can first note that the values of $\pi_{G \rightarrow L_c}$ for the three pure alcohols are nearly the same (~ 0.3 dynes/cm) and have a little tendency to increase with temperature. Further, the $\pi_{L_c \rightarrow S}$ for C_{16} -OH and C_{18} -OH are ~ 10 dynes/cm and ~ 13.0 dynes/cm respectively and which again increase only slightly with temperature in the range 15° - 25° . But for C_{22} -OH, a significant difference is observed in that the $\pi_{L_c \rightarrow S}$ is nearly doubled (i.e., from 11.2 to 20.2 dynes/cm) when the temperature is raised from 15° to 20° , the corresponding change in the interval 20° to 25° being about 3 dynes/cm, which is also much more than what happened (~ 0.5 dynes/cm) in the cases of C_{16} -OH and C_{18} -OH under similar conditions.

While the actual area values corresponding to $\pi_{L_c \rightarrow S}$ are all comparable in the three cases, their increase for C_{22} -OH is much more (18.43 to 19.16 i.e., 0.73 \AA^2) than those of C_{16} -OH ($\sim 0.12 \text{ \AA}^2$) and of C_{18} -OH ($\sim 0.23 \text{ \AA}^2$) for a rise of temperature from 15° to 20° . This result may be taken as an indication of the existence of the weakest van der Waals forces in the C_{22} -OH system and its rapid fall with temperature producing high spreading pressure (π) as observed. Simultaneously if the hydrogen bonding interaction is considered very weak in this case, the increase of temperature (from 15° to 20°) may be sufficient to break the bond with a consequent change of orientation of the molecules such that the

charged atoms in the dipolar OH groups in neighbouring molecules face each other (Fig. 9) to effectively produce a repulsive interaction and enhanced spreading pressure.

Considering now the isotherms of the three compositions of the two mixed systems ($C_{16}\text{-OH} + C_{22}\text{-OH}$ and $C_{18}\text{-OH} + C_{22}\text{-OH}$), one can notice the appearance of an additional phase (LS) and correspondingly three transition points $\pi_{G \rightarrow L_c}$, $\pi_{L_c \rightarrow LS}$ and $\pi_{LS \rightarrow S}$. The values of $\pi_{G \rightarrow L_c}$ differ very little from those of the pure components. However, though the $\pi_{L_c \rightarrow S}$ values are comparable but these are significantly lower than the $\pi_{L_c \rightarrow S}$ transition pressures of the pure components. The corresponding area values at these points are larger and perhaps this gives rise to a little orientational freedom of the film molecules and thus facilitate their association through hydrogen bonding and reduce the spreading tendency as indicated by lowering of $\pi_{L_c \rightarrow LS}$. The $\pi_{LS \rightarrow S}$ transition pressures are much higher than the $\pi_{L_c \rightarrow S}$ of the pure components, again pointing to the fact that due to dissimilar molecules in the film, the overall intermolecular attractions are much reduced as a result of which there is observed a large increase of $\pi_{LS \rightarrow S}$ values.

The relative changes in the thermal area expansion coefficient (β) presented in Table 3, can be taken as a qualitative measure of the intermolecular forces between the film molecules. For the pure alcohols, β is positive except for $C_{22}\text{-OH}$ in the temperature range $20^\circ\text{--}25^\circ$ where as at all the chosen pressures β is negative. Further β increases steadily with the increase of the chain length of the molecules indicating overall weaker attraction between them. The contraction (β negative) of the $C_{22}\text{-OH}$ film is attributed to the polymorphic transition to a more closely packed structure. It can also be speculated that at low surface pressures, the $C_{22}\text{-OH}$ molecules are clustered through hydrogen bonding. This being weak, breaks above 20° , allowing stronger chain-chain van der Waals interactions and formation of more close-packed structure.

The β values in the cases of the mixed films at surface pressures of 2, 4, 14, 26 and 34 dynes/cm. have been calculated from the respective values of area from the π - A isotherms at 15° , 20° and 25° . The results have been indicated with positive sign (expansion) and negative sign (contraction) in the table 6.

TABLE 6

Film area expansion coefficient $\beta = \Delta A/\Delta T$ of the mixed systems $C_{16}\text{-OH} + C_{22}\text{-OH}$ and $C_{18}\text{-OH} + C_{22}\text{-OH}$

System	Temperature range, $^\circ\text{C}$	Mole fraction of $C_{22}\text{-OH}$				
		0.0	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.0
$C_{16}\text{-OH}$	15-20	+	-	+	+	+
	20-25	+	+	+	+	-
$C_{18}\text{-OH}$	15-20	+	+	-	-	+
	20-25	+	+	-	-	-

The above results may also be explained on the basis of the factors mentioned earlier.

Referring to the results presented in tables 4 and 5 and Figs. 7 and 8, it is clearly demonstrated that the positive and negative deviations from the ideal mixture law depend on the nature of the film forming molecules, composition of the mixed films, surface pressure and temperature of the monolayers. The variation of area/molecule indicating the formation of expanded or closer-packed structure in the mixed monolayer state seems to occur as a result of physical change involving rearrangement of the molecules of one constituent with respect to the other and formation of different types of surface lattices. The molecular areas represent the different modes of packing of the chain molecules. The polymorphic behaviour of these compounds in the bulk state has been well established from X-ray studies¹³. Since the three alcohols have more or less the same shape and size, the concept of one type of molecules occupying the intermolecular cavities formed by the other to explain the apparent condensed structure in the mixed monolayers is not applicable here. The added component would occupy the substitutional position with or without modification of the lattice structure.

The observations of the maxima or minima in the curves in Fig. 7 and also the minima observed in the free energy plots (Fig. 8) need not be associated with the formation of any complex having definite proportions in the usual chemical sense. The lowering of free energy of mixing can as well arise from closer packing of molecules forming a more stable lattice in the mixed film state.

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